

Design and synthesis of series of receptors and their use in extraction and liquid membrane transport studies of amino acids

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Abstract : A series of non-cyclic receptors 1,5-bis-(2-naphthyl)oxy-3-oxapentane (P_1), 1,8-bis-(2-naphthyl)oxy-3,6-dioxaoctane (P_2) and 1,11-bis-(2-naphthyl)oxy-3,6,9-trioxaundecane (P_3) have been synthesized and tested as carriers for the comparative extraction and transport studies of amino acids (glycine, valine, alanine and threonine) through chloroform bulk liquid membrane system. Effects of various parameters such as variation in concentration of amino acid as well as receptor, effect of chain length and nature of amino acid under study have been investigated. The non-cyclic receptors with different flexible binding sites present hydrogen bonding and π -stacking interactions with amino acids. The distribution ratio, flux and transport efficiency were also determined. The sequence of extraction abilities of receptors P_1 , P_2 and P_3 for valine, alanine and glycine was found to be $P_1 > P_2 > P_3$, $P_1 > P_2 \gg P_3$ whereas for threonine, the trend was $P_1 > P_3 > P_2$. The trend of transport abilities of receptors P_1 , P_2 and P_3 for valine, alanine and threonine was observed to be $P_3 > P_2 > P_1$ whereas for glycine the trend was $P_2 > P_3 > P_1$. The amount of amino acid extracted and transported depends mainly on the structure, concentration of receptor, amino acid and also on the lipophilicity of amino acids.

Keywords : Amino acid, design, receptors, synthesis, extraction.

Introduction

Supramolecular chemistry is based principally on the concept of molecular recognition, which is defined as a process of selective binding and selection of substrate by a receptor. Supramolecular systems for the transport of biologically active agents i.e. drug delivery, amino acid purification, etc. have been singled out and are most promising for science and industry at present. Participation of amino acids in great variety of metabolic processes and biochemical processes make them most studied compounds, especially regarding their transport through biological membranes. Their permeation through biological membrane usually mediated by protein carriers buried in the biomembrane depends on their predominantly hydrophilic character¹. Bulk liquid membranes are used to investigate the complexation chemistry and transport processes of synthetic and natural receptors². Macrocyclic receptors, lipophilic ionic carriers^{3,4}, podands have been employed as selective carriers in these membranes^{5,6}. Podands containing naphthyl end group and variable polyether chain show superior binding and selectivity to-

wards neutral molecules. The binding efficiency and selectivity of podands for metal ions has earlier been reported by Vogtle *et al.*⁷. Earlier work has revealed that non-cyclic oligoethylene glycols i.e. podands form stoichiometric complexes with alkali metal picrates⁸. These types of podands behave as good chromogenic receptors and further studies can be progressed in analytical field.

Research concerning selective transport of amino acids and their derivatives through liquid membranes using calixarenes⁹, chiral receptors⁶, quaternary ammonium salts, metal complexes¹⁰ and crown ethers¹¹ as carriers have been reported. The bulk liquid membrane system for the transport and extraction of metal ions (alkali and alkaline) and amino acids with non-cyclic receptors as carriers has been reported^{12,13}.

These non-cyclic podands are synthetic mimics of naturally occurring antibodies like monensin, and lasalocids. This piece of work has been planned with the objective to design and synthesize simple podands which could be placed in between a highly specific molecular recognition

system and non specific glycols. Molecular recognition process can be monitored by designing and tailoring the receptors having end groups with required properties. With this series of ligands our aim is to design non-cyclic receptors for different substrates i.e. alkali and alkaline earth metal ions and neutral substrates with the introduction of flexibility and naphthyl end groups and employed them as extractants as well as carriers for the selected amino acids through chloroform bulk liquid membrane system.

Scheme 1

Experimental

Analytical grade amino acids (glycine, valine, alanine and threonine) were obtained from Ranbaxy (India). The reagents used in the synthesis of non-cyclic receptors were 1-butanol, KOH, 2-naphthol, bis-(1,2-chloroethoxyethane), 1,11-dichloro-3,6,9-trioxaundecane (Merck). KCl, NaOH and $MgSO_4$ were purchased from s. d. fine Chemicals (India). Analytical grade $CHCl_3$ was received from Qualigens and used without further purification. Melting point was measured by the melting point apparatus (Boss 165). Elemental analysis (C, H, N) were obtained from CDRI, Lucknow using elemental analyzer (Carlo Erba 1108). IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer (Perkin-Elmer Bx 70836) and 1H NMR spectra were recorded in $D_2O/CDCl_3$ using TMS as internal reference at CDRI, Lucknow at 400 MHz. Spectrophotometer (Varian 350) was employed for the estimation of amino acid.

Estimation of amino acid :

The 0.5 mL aqueous amino acid (0.1 M) was taken in 10 mL standard flask and the 0.2 mL ninhydrin solution (0.5%) was added and kept in the boiling water for 10 min. Thereafter, 6 mL of 60% ethanol was added with

double distilled water until the total volume was 10 mL. In this way calibration curve was plotted ranging from $1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$ to $1.0 \times 10^{-1} M$ at λ_{max} 570 nm¹⁴.

Synthesis of receptor (P_2) :

In a round bottom flask, 150 mL 1-butanol solution, KOH 3.36 g (0.60 mol), 2-naphthol 8.64 g (0.06 mol) and bis-(1,2-chloroethoxyethane) 4.68 mL (0.03 mol) were added one by one. The reaction mixture was refluxed in a round bottom flask at 120 °C for 20 h (Scheme 1).

After the completion of reaction, precipitated KCl was filtered off. The filtrate was taken up in chloroform and washed 3–4 times with dilute NaOH and deionised water. The organic phase was separated by means of solvent extraction, dried over $MgSO_4$. White shiny crystals, yield 3.8 g (42.0%), m.p. 80 °C (Found : C, 77.5; H, 6.5. Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{26}O_4$ (mol. wt. 402) : C, 77.6; H, 6.4%); IR (KBr) (ν cm^{-1}) : 2924, 2872 (C-H), 1253 (Ar-O-CH₂), 1114, 1055 (CH₂-O-CH₂), 967 (aromatic ring); 1H NMR ($CDCl_3$) : δ 3.79 (4H, s, -O-CH₂-O-CH₂), 4.45 (2H, t, Ar-OCH₂), 7.75 (7H, m, naphthyl C-H); FAB mass : m/z molecular ion peak (402). Calcd. for $C_{26}H_{26}O_4$ (mol. wt. 402).

Synthesis of receptor (P_1 and P_3) :

Synthesis of receptor P_3 and P_1 was done by refluxing 1,11-dichloro-3,6,9-trioxaundecane 4.74 mL (0.29 mol) and 2,2-dichlorodiethylether 3.8 mL (0.02 mol) with 2-naphthol 8.64 g (0.06 mol) respectively under the same conditions as mentioned above.

Receptor (P_3) :

Brown solid, yield 6.5 g (52%), m.p. 54 °C (Found : C, 75.4; H, 6.8. Calcd. for $C_{28}H_{30}O_5$ (mol. wt. 446) : C, 75.3; H, 6.7%); IR (KBr) (ν cm^{-1}) : 3056, 2900 (C-H),

Table 1. Amount of amino acids (1-4) extracted into organic phase after 4 h with receptors (P₁-P₃) in chloroform

Source phase : 10 mL amino acid solution

Concentration of amino acid = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Receptor concentration = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ (P₁-P₃) in 15 mL chloroform

Concentration of amino acid ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	Receptor P ₁		Receptor P ₂		Receptor P ₃	
	Amount of amino acid extracted ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	D_m	Amount of amino acid extracted ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	D_m	Amount of amino acid extracted ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	D_m
Alanine						
3.0	1.09	0.5021	1.06	0.5913	1.02	0.5321
4.0	1.87	0.5811	1.44	0.6232	1.21	0.5643
5.0	2.14	0.6793	2.10	0.6666	2.00	0.6349
6.0	2.11	0.6682	2.05	0.6457	1.90	0.6172
Glycine						
3.0	0.95	0.2677	0.80	0.2525	0.29	0.0516
4.0	1.03	0.2886	1.00	0.2751	0.51	0.0946
5.0	1.70	0.3505	1.60	0.3298	0.55	0.1030
6.0	1.57	0.3248	1.42	0.2921	0.45	0.0972
Threonine						
3.0	0.44	0.2087	0.35	0.1675	0.21	0.1343
4.0	0.55	0.2141	0.39	0.1936	0.27	0.1476
5.0	0.65	0.2321	0.42	0.2154	0.50	0.1745
6.0	0.58	0.2156	0.37	0.1879	0.45	0.1576
Valine						
3.0	2.20	0.6342	1.35	0.5671	1.02	0.3712
4.0	2.34	0.6585	2.05	0.6554	1.23	0.3978
5.0	2.70	0.7297	2.59	0.7001	1.65	0.4459
6.0	2.55	0.7043	2.43	0.6541	1.55	0.3597

Table 2. Amount of amino acids (1-4) transported into aqueous phase after 24 h with receptor (P₁-P₃) in chloroform

Source phase : 10 mL amino acid solution

Concentration of amino acid = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Receptor concentration = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ (P₁-P₃) in 15 mL chloroform

Concentration of amino acid ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	Receptor P ₁		Receptor P ₂		Receptor P ₃	
	Amount of amino acid transported ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	J_m ($\times 10^{-4}$ mol/m ² s)	Amount of amino acid transported ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	J_m ($\times 10^{-4}$ mol/m ² s)	Amount of amino acid transported ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	J_m ($\times 10^{-4}$ mol/m ² s)
Alanine						
3.0	0.55	0.7779	0.45	0.6378	0.85	1.204
4.0	0.90	0.9921	0.95	1.346	1.06	1.502
5.0	1.04	1.442	1.18	1.612	1.28	1.814
6.0	1.00	1.356	1.12	1.500	1.18	1.621
Glycine						
3.0	0.64	0.9112	0.80	1.135	0.75	1.062
4.0	0.83	1.1761	0.95	1.342	0.93	1.317
5.0	1.00	1.4170	1.20	1.625	1.15	1.559
6.0	0.90	1.284	1.10	1.526	1.05	1.376

Table-2 (contd.)

Threonine						
3.0	0.30	0.4252	0.41	0.5811	0.57	0.8085
4.0	0.40	0.5659	0.59	0.9012	0.63	0.9779
5.0	0.65	0.9212	0.90	1.1333	0.95	1.624
6.0	0.55	0.9052	0.80	1.1033	0.78	1.364
Valine						
3.0	0.63	0.9056	0.92	1.286	0.95	1.346
4.0	0.94	1.332	1.03	1.459	1.15	1.629
5.0	1.06	1.473	1.25	1.973	1.39	2.055
6.0	1.00	1.324	1.15	1.735	1.25	1.965

1255 (Ar-O-CH₂), 1184, 1052 (CH₂-O-CH₂), 967 (naphthyl C-H); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 3.8 (4H, s, CH₂-O-CH₂), 4.42 (2H, t, Ar-O-CH₂), 7.75 (7H, m, naphthyl C-H); FAB mass : *m/z* molecular ion peak (446). Calcd. for C₂₈H₃₀O₅ (mol. wt. 446).

Receptor (P₁) :

Synthesis of receptor P₁ was done by refluxing 2,2-dichlorodiethylether 3.8 mL (0.02 mol) with 2-naphthol 8.64 g (0.06 mol) respectively under the same conditions as mentioned above (Scheme 1). White crystalline solid, yield 2.5 g (33.4 %), m. p. 132 °C (Found : C, 80.3; H, 6.3. Calcd. for C₂₄H₂₂O₃ (mol. wt. 358) : C, 80.4; H, 6.1%); IR (KBr) (ν cm⁻¹) : 3050, 2949 (C-H), 1260 (Ar-O-CH₂), 1184, 1080, 1056 (CH₂-O-CH₂), 968 (naphthyl C-H); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 3.58 (4H, s, -O-CH₂-O-CH₂), 4.12 (2H, t, Ar-O-CH₂), 7.3 (7H, m, aromatic C-H).

Extraction studies :

10 mL of 5 × 10⁻³ M aqueous amino acid solution was vigorously stirred with 10 mL of 1 × 10⁻⁴ M receptor solution in chloroform in a 50 mL beaker for 4 h on a magnetic stirrer at 25 °C. After stirring, the mixture was allowed to stand for 5 min for the separation of two phases and the aqueous phase analysed for extracted amino acid by determining the difference in the concentration of amino acid in aqueous phase before and after extraction. Distribution coefficient was calculated by using eq. (1).

$$D_m = \frac{\text{Total concentration of amino acid in organic phase}}{\text{Total concentration of amino acid in aqueous phase}} \quad (1)$$

Transport studies :

Transport studies were performed in a "U" tube glass

cell¹⁵ at 25 °C. 15 mL of chloroform containing 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M of receptor was taken as membrane phase. The source phase was composed of 10 mL of 5.0 × 10⁻³ M of aqueous amino acid in one limb of the "U" tube and 10 mL of double distilled water served as the receiving phase in the other limb. The membrane phase was constantly stirred for 24 h. Flux was calculated by using eq. (2).

$$J_m = \frac{C_{(\text{rec.})}V}{At} \quad (2)$$

where *C* is concentration of amino acid in receiving phase (mol/dm³), *V* is volume of receiving phase (mol/dm³), *A* is effective area of membrane (m²) and *t* is time (s).

Results and discussion

The blank experiments for the extraction and transport studies of each amino acid in which membrane was devoid of carrier, no leakage of amino acid from the source phase into the receiving phase was observed. All measurements were performed in triplicate to check reproducibility. In order to find out the optimal concentration of amino acid for transport and extraction studies, concentration of amino acid was varied from 3.0 × 10⁻³ M to 5.0 × 10⁻³ M at constant receptor concentration (1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M). For optimization of the receptor, the concentration was varied from 1.0 × 10⁻¹ M to 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M at constant amino acid concentration (5.0 × 10⁻³ M). The optimal concentration for amino acid and receptor were found to be 5.0 × 10⁻³ M and 1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M respectively.

Figs. 2 and 3 depict the results of transport and extraction studies of amino acids with receptors (P₁-P₃) at optimum concentration using CHCl₃ bulk liquid membrane. As is evident from the Fig. 2, the trend of extraction abilities of receptors P₁, P₂ and P₃ for valine, ala-

Fig. 1. Molecular recognition of amino acids with non cyclic receptors P_1 , P_2 and P_3 : (a) $O\cdots H$ hydrogen bonding and (b) van der Waals interactions between side chain of amino acid and naphthalene ring of receptors.

ety of amino acid and donor oxygen sites of the receptor^{16,17}. The receptor P_1 is more rigid as compared to receptors P_2 and P_3 due to its shorter chain length that acts as anchoring points for hydrogen bonding interactions. The extraction of amino acids observed to follow the sequence of hydrophobicity scale i.e. val > ala > gly > thr¹⁸. Threonine displays less extraction due to its hydrophilic character in comparison to other amino acids. Higher flux has been observed for hydrophobic amino acids as compared to less hydrophobic ones.

The sequence of transport abilities of receptors P_1 , P_2 and P_3 for valine, alanine and threonine observed was $P_3 > P_2 > P_1$ while for glycine, the trend observed was $P_2 > P_3 > P_1$. Among the receptors P_1 , P_2 and P_3 , if we compare the lipophilicity and flexibility then receptor P_3 exhibits more lipophilic and flexible character due to in-

Fig. 2. Amount of amino acid extracted with receptors P_1 , P_2 and P_3 : concentration of amino acid in source phase = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, concentration of receptor P_1 , P_2 and P_3 = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ (P_1 - P_3) in 15 mL chloroform.

nine and glycine is observed to be $P_1 > P_2 > P_3$, $P_1 > P_2 \gg P_3$ whereas for threonine the trend was $P_1 > P_3 > P_2$ respectively. The receptors P_1 , P_2 and P_3 possess di-, tri- and tetraethylene glycol chain length with rigid naphthyl end groups. The receptors (P_1 - P_3) interact with amino acids by hydrogen bonding between $-NH_4^+$ moi-

ety of amino acid and donor oxygen sites of the receptor as compared to receptor P_2 with four donor oxygen atoms and P_1 having three oxygen atoms. The receptor P_3 showed better carrier ability for amino acids due to its increased chain length and more binding sites for hydrogen bonding interaction^{16,19}.

Fig. 3. Amount of amino acid transported with receptors P_1 , P_2 and P_3 : concentration of amino acid = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, concentration of receptor P_1 , P_2 and P_3 = $1.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ (P_1 - P_3) in 15 mL chloroform.

The possible sites for the interaction of amino acids with selected receptors are given in Fig. 1. The hydrophobic exterior and flexible donor sites with most suited conformation of receptor P_3 facilitates the easy passage of amino acid receptor complex from the organic phase to aqueous receiving phase thus results in better transport of amino acids. Besides, this π -stacking interactions may enhance the carrier ability of receptor P_3 ¹⁷. The receptor P_1 with few binding sites due to short chain length is responsible for poor transport ability. Molecular interactions are more feasible in receptor P_3 as compared to receptors P_1 and P_2 . The receptor P_3 has more binding sites required for stability hence isolated complexes are reported with P_3 in solid state, while the receptors P_1 and P_2 act as a carrier and fails to isolate complexes with amino acids.

Hence, it is clear that the decrease in amount of amino acid in the source phase is not compensating with that of in receiving phase, which is an indication of accumulation of amino acid in the membrane²⁰. Thus, the structural parameters of receptors i.e. chain length and end group of the receptors play an important role in the transport of amino acids, while nature and hydrophobicity of amino acid decides the extraction ability of amino acids.

Conclusion :

Thus, it can be concluded, the receptor that shows better transport efficiency shows poor extractability. The

receptor P_1 is selective extractant for valine and alanine and receptor P_3 proved to be the best carrier for valine. The governing factors in studies are the active donor binding sites of the receptor P_1 that are responsible for the formation of stable amino acid receptor complex which accounts for its good extraction ability. This series of non-cyclic receptors with naphthyl end groups present π -stacking interactions that enhances the carrier ability of the receptor compared to simple glycols as reported earlier. It emphasizes the ability of synthesized acyclic receptors containing rigid naphthyl end groups to recognize the biologically important amino acids.

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